

Wavelength of ultrasound DNA waves propagating without needing to matter within a microphone/speaker like cell

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Abstract: We show that DNAs within cells act like the inductors within speakers/microphones and emit ultrasound waves. Frequencies of these waves are more than frequencies of light waves and their wavelengths are smaller than size of air molecules. Thus, these waves pass molecules of air and propagate without needing to matter. In fact, DNA ultrasound waves are longitudinal waves which act like transverse electromagnetic waves and move in any type of vacuum. These waves could be taken by some other DNAs and cause to the growth rate of bacteria. We test idea and show that bacteria within two vessels of milk communicate with each other and exchange ultrasound waves.

I. Introduction

Up to date, the effects of ultrasound and sound waves on biological systems have been considered extensively. For example, some authors have considered the effects of ultrasound waves on tumor growth reduction and DNA [1]. Some other authors have shown that sound waves could control the rate of bacterial growth [2]. They have considered the relation between type and frequency of sound waves with growth of different types of bacteria [2]. In another research, authors have shown that the efficiency of the combination of ultrasonic waves under pressure with heat (MTS) for bacterial spore inactivation is directly correlated with the thermal resistance. Also, they revealed that MTS treatment is capable of inactivating spore-forming bacteria and that the inactivation efficiency of the combined treatment is correlated with the thermal resistance of the spore species [3]. In another paper, authors have developed the new methodology of strategic ultrasound treatment on lactic acid bacteria (LAB) to induce stress response for the enhancement of β -glucosidase activity that can be used for the biotransformation of glucosides into aglycones isoflavones in soy milk [4]. In another investigation, ultrasound application on bacterial inactivation in municipal wastewater (MWW) have been evaluated [5]. In another work, it has been shown that by

combinations of ultrasound, hydrogen peroxide, and active lactoperoxidase system, microbiota and selected spoilage and pathogenic bacteria in milk become inactive [6]. In other article, diagnostic accuracy of ultrasound scanning for prenatal microcephaly in the context of Zika Virus Infection has been considered [7]. In another research, authors have compared the clinical characteristics and imaging features on contrast-enhanced ultrasound (CEUS) of hepatitis B virus (HBV)-related combined hepatocellular–cholangiocarcinoma (CHC) and hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) [8]. Motivated by these researches, we estimate the frequency of ultrasound waves emitted by DNAs within cells and consider its role on evolutions of biological systems.

The outline of this papers is as follows: In section II, we calculate frequency of emitted ultrasound waves from DNAs and determine its shape. In section III, we propose a method to test the model for bacterial DNAs within the milk container. In section IV, we consider results. In section V, we discuss about the origin of results. The last section is devoted to conclusion.

II. Frequency and wavelength of DNA ultrasound waves within cells

Each DNA is formed from joining charged particles and according to laws of physics, by motion of these charges within cells, some electromagnetic waves are emerged. Thus, a DNA could act like the receiver or sender of radio waves [9]. The structure of this molecule is similar to the inductor and can emit or take magnetic fields (See figure 1). If we compare the structure of a DNA within the cell, we notice that it is similar to an inductor within the speaker or microphone. In a speaker, an inductor interacts with a magnet, vibrate and cause to motion of a plastic. Motion of this plastic causes to the motion of molecules of air and emergence of sound. Within a cell , a DNA interacts with proteins, RNAs, nuclear membranes and other biological molecules, vibrate and produce sound and ultrasound waves (See figure 1).

Fig1: Similarity between DNAs within cells and speaker\microphones

In this section, we try to calculate frequency and wavelength of DNA sound/ultrasound waves. First, we calculate magnetic fields which are emitted by DNAs within cells. We assume that a DNA acts like an inductor and thus, we write below equation for its magnetic field:

$$\mathbf{B}_{DNA} = \mu_0 \mathbf{n}_{gene} \mathbf{I}_{gene} \quad (1)$$

Where n_{gene} is the density of genes [10] within DNAs and I_{gene} are currents which move along genes. We assume that each gene is in fact a long wire that is coiled around the axis of a DNA. A DNA may have 50000 or more gene (N_{gene}) [10] and each gene has round 10^{-12} meter long (L_{gene}) within a cell. Thus, we can calculate density of genes (n_{gene}):

$$\mathbf{n}_{gene} = \mathbf{N}_{gene} / \mathbf{L}_{gene} \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{N}_{gene} = 50000 [10] \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{L}_{gene} = 10^{-12} \text{m} [11,12] \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{n}_{gene} = 5 \times 10^{16} \quad (5)$$

To calculate current along genes, we should calculate total effective charge of all genes (Q_{gene}) and their velocity (V_{gene}).

$$I_{\text{gene}} = Q_{\text{gene}} V_{\text{gene}} \quad (6)$$

Effective charges of all genes are different from their normal total charge. A gene may have a few normal charges, because its charges cancel the effect of each other in static state. However, during the gene expression and DNA evolutions, each charge has a separate effect. For this reason, we should regard total charges of all genes. To obtain this charge, we should write:

$$Q_{\text{gene}} = N_{\text{gene}} q_{\text{gene}} \quad (7)$$

Where N_{gene} is the number of genes and q_{gene} is the effective charge of a gene. Again, we insist that effective charge of a gene is different from its normal charge. In fact, we should regard all electrons and atoms that contribute in gene expression. For this reason, we should write:

$$q_{\text{gene}} = N_{\text{base}} q_{\text{base}} \quad (8)$$

where N_{base} is the number of base pairs within a gene [13,14] and q_{base} is the electrical charge of a base. We can put approximate numbers and obtain effective charge of all genes:

$$N_{\text{base}} = 10^9 [13,14] \quad (9)$$

$$q_{\text{base}} = (10-20) q_{\text{electron}} = (10-20) \times 1/6 \times 10^{-19} \quad (10)$$

$$Q_{\text{gene}} = 5 \times 10^{-5} \quad (11)$$

Now, we calculate effective velocity genes:

$$V_{\text{gene}} = L_{\text{gene}} \omega_{\text{gene}} \quad (12)$$

This velocity depends on the length of a gene (L_{gene}) and its rotating velocity (ω_{gene}).

$$L_{\text{gene}} = 10^{-12} \text{m} [11,12] \quad (13)$$

The rotating velocity of a gene (ω_{gene}) can be obtained by summing over rotating velocity of all its effective charges (ω_{charge}):

$$\omega_{\text{gene}} = n_{\text{charge}} \omega_{\text{charge}} \quad (14)$$

To obtain number of charges, we multiply number of bases and number of atoms/electrons

$$n_{\text{charge}} = N_{\text{base}} N_{\text{atom}} \quad (15)$$

Now, we put approximate values for numbers and obtain velocity of genes:

$$N_{\text{base}} = 10^9 [13,14] \quad (16)$$

$$N_{\text{atom}} = 10 \quad (17)$$

$$n_{\text{charge}} = 10^{10} \quad (18)$$

$$\omega_{\text{charge}} = 2\pi/T_{\text{charge}} \quad (19)$$

$$T_{\text{charge}} = .1 \quad (20)$$

$$\omega_{\text{charge}} = 6.28 \times 10 \quad (21)$$

$$V_{\text{gene}} = 6.28 \times 10^{-1} \quad (22)$$

Substituting values of velocity from equation (22) and charges from equation (11) in equation (6), we can obtain current of genes:

$$I_{\text{gene}} = 3.14 \times 10^{-4} \quad (23)$$

Putting the current from above equation (6) and density of genes in from equation (5) in equation (1), we calculate magnetic field of a DNA within a cell.

$$B_{\text{DNA}} = 985.96 \times 10^5 = 10^8 \quad (24)$$

Using this field, we can obtain energy density of magnetic fields around a DNA within a cell.

$$\mu_0 = 4\pi \times 10^{-7} \quad (25)$$

$$U_B = (B^2/2 \mu_0) = 1.59 \times 10^{22} \quad (26)$$

At this stage, we assume that a DNA is similar to an inductor and calculate total energy of magnetic field around a DNA.

$$E_B = U_B V_{\text{DNA}} \quad (27)$$

$$V_{\text{DNA}} = 2\pi [R_{\text{DNA}} + x_{\text{DNA}}][L_{\text{DNA}} + x_{\text{DNA}}] \quad (28)$$

$$E_B = (B^2/2 \mu_0) 2\pi [R_{\text{DNA}} + x_{\text{DNA}}][L_{\text{DNA}} + x_{\text{DNA}}] \quad (29)$$

Where R_{DNA} is the radius of DNA inductor, L_{DNA} is the length of DNA inductor and x_{DNA} is a distance that DNA oscillate, go ahead and go back. Using this energy, we can obtain forces (F_{DNA}) which are created by vibration of a DNA inductor:

$$F_{DNA} = d E_B / dx_{DNA} = [(B^2/2 \mu_0) 2\pi] x_{DNA} + [(B^2/2 \mu_0) 2\pi] [R_{DNA} + L_{DNA}] \quad (30)$$

Where (K_{DNA}) is a constant depending on magnetic field:

$$K_{DNA} = [(B^2/2 \mu_0) 2\pi] = 9.98 \times 10^{22} = 10^{23} \quad (31)$$

$$F_{DNA} = K_{DNA} x_{DNA} + [(B^2/2 \mu_0) 2\pi] [R_{DNA} + L_{DNA}] \quad (32)$$

Using this force, we can obtain frequency of oscillation. These oscillations cause to emergence of ultrasound waves which their frequencies are equal to frequencies of DNA vibrations :

$$\Omega_{Ultrasound} = [K_{DNA}/M_{DNA}]^{1/2} \quad (33)$$

$$M_{DNA} = 3.59 \times 10^{-15} \quad [15] \quad (34)$$

$$\Omega_{Ultrasound} = 2.7 \times 10^{18} \quad (35)$$

$$v_{Ultrasound} = \Omega_{Ultrasound}/2\pi = 4.4 \times 10^{17} \quad (36)$$

Frequency of waves have reverse relation with their frequencies.

$$\lambda_{Ultrasound} = 1/v_{Ultrasound} = 10^{-17} \quad (37)$$

This is very nice result that we obtain from our model. This equation shows that wave-length of ultrasound waves is around (10^{-17} m) which is very smaller of size of air molecules (10^{-10}) [16] (See figure 2). Thus, these waves could pass air molecules. Thus, these waves don't need to matters for propagating and could move in any vacuum like the electromagnetic waves which move without needing to matter.

Fig 2: Ultrasound waves of a DNA within a cell are very smaller than size of the air molecules

III. Materials and method

Material

The needed materials for testing this idea are:

1. Two vessels
2. Milk
3. Thermometer
4. Scopes and Amperemeter
5. Graphene sheet
6. Metal
7. Copper wire
8. Magnets

Methods:

1. First, we pour milk into two vessels and keep them in a temperature around 38° C.

2. We put two magnets in two sides of a metal and produce two magnetic fields with two opposite directions. Electrons become parallel with external fields and some of electrons with opposite spins in barrier, become pair.
3. We can use of a graphene sheet instead of metal.
4. We connect metal or graphene sheet to an scope like Radio-SkyPipe and amperemeter.
5. We put one of vessels on metal and measure currents by scope.
6. We bring other vessel near first one and measure currents again (See Figure 3)

Fig 3. A circuit for taking signals of bacteria within milk

IV. Results

In figure 4, we show radiated signals of vessel of milk. It is clear that by passing time, bacteria grow and emit more ultrasound waves. These waves break spin pairs and produce some currents. In Fig 5, we compare the growth of radiated signals for two states. In one state, we only measure currents which are produced by ultrasound waves of bacteria within a vessel of milk. In second state, we consider effects of exchanged ultrasound waves between bacteria within two vessels of milk. It is clear that bacteria communicate with each other and exchange ultrasound waves. This causes that rate of their growth grows and more signals are observed by scopes.

Fig 4. Radiated signals of a vessel of milk after keeping it at 38-40° C

Fig 5. Comparing signals of bacteria within milk, for one vessel (blue color) and two vessels (red color).

Discussion:

Up to date, it has been assumed that some transverse waves like electromagnetic ones propagate in a vacuum without needing to matter, while longitudinal waves need to matter. However, our calculations and results show that wavelength of some DNA ultrasound waves are smaller of the size of air molecules and couldn't move them. These waves could be taken by DNAs of other cells and play the main role in growth rate of bacteria. In fact, a DNA within the cell acts like an inductor within the microphone. This DNA inductor interact with biological matters and nuclear membranes, oscillate and produce some longitudinal waves. These waves could break some spin pairs and we couldn't observe their effects on the scope.

Conclusion

In this paper, we have shown that DNAs within cells emit some ultrasound waves which move in a vacuum without matter and only could be detected by circuits of other DNAs. To this aim, we have simulated DNAs within cells with some inductors within speakers/microphones. In a speaker, inductors interact with external files, vibrate and cause to motion of a plastic. Vibration of this plastic leads to motion of air molecules and emergence of sound. Similarly, a DNA interacts with proteins and other biological matters within a cell, vibrate and produce ultrasound waves. These waves are smaller of molecules of airs and couldn't move them. They move without needing to matter and act like electromagnetic waves. These waves could be taken by circuits of other DNAs and play the main role in microbial growth. We have considered effects of ultrasound DNA waves on the growth of bacteria and taken their signals.

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